

Active Neutrality and the Limits of Abstention:

Cognitive and Normative Dimensions of Non-Intervention in Hate Speech Contexts

Abstract

This paper offers a recognition-dependent account of neutrality in hate and exclusionary speech contexts, showing that silence and non-intervention are often socially unintelligible as neutral and can unintentionally reinforce harm. It explains why neutrality cannot be self-declared, why silence is especially vulnerable to misinterpretation in conditions of inequality, and why recognition plays a constitutive role in whether neutrality obtains. Theoretically, it distinguishes passive from active neutrality, framing neutrality as a socially mediated achievement rather than an internal stance. Methodologically, it integrates philosophy of language, social epistemology, social cognition, and empirical moral psychology to analyse how silence and non-intervention are interpreted in non-ideal contexts. Rather than assessing the ethical rightness of neutrality under constrained agency, the paper identifies the conditions under which silence and non-intervention fail as vehicles of neutrality and clarifies how neutrality can be sustained without reinforcing injustice.

Introduction

Neutrality is among the most frequently invoked concepts in contemporary ethical, social, and political debate, and one that has been extensively theorised within political philosophy, ethics and the philosophy of science. What has received comparatively less sustained attention, however, is *how ordinary people understand, interpret, and practically navigate neutrality in situated social contexts*. In everyday moral reasoning, neutrality is commonly taken to consist in non-interference: to remain neutral is to refrain from judgement, intervention, or alignment in the face of disagreement or conflict. Silence, hesitation, and abstention are therefore often treated as morally safe options—ways of avoiding coercion, moral overreach, or the imposition of contested values.

To examine these practices more concretely, this paper operationalises non-interference in hate speech contexts as silence and non-intervention. Silence involves refraining from verbal objection, while non-intervention involves not taking action through formal or group-based avenues. This captures the forms of non-interference most relevant to everyday encounters with hateful or exclusionary speech, where direct engagement is often constrained by social norms, unequal power relations, or risks of escalation. Research in social psychology on bystander behaviour shows that ordinary people who aim to remain neutral often choose

silence or non-intervention as a behavioural strategy when they do not see clear cues to act, or wish to avoid taking a side.¹

Despite its intuitive appeal, this picture of neutrality relies on a strong idealisation. It presupposes that abstention leaves the normative landscape unchanged—that by not intervening, one avoids influencing outcomes. Yet a substantial body of work in philosophy of language and social epistemology has shown that this presupposition rarely holds in actual social environments². Silence and non-intervention are routinely observed, interpreted, and evaluated against background norms of cooperation, authority, uptake, and differential vulnerability. They can thereby shape what is taken to be permissible, acceptable, or endorsed within a conversational and social context.³ In many ordinary settings, failing to object is not treated as normatively inert, but as a meaningful social signal—one that can license, entrench, or amplify objectionable norms even in the absence of any intention to do so.⁴

This tension becomes especially salient in socially charged situations marked by uncertainty or ambiguity, like those involving false, hateful, or exclusionary speech. Unchallenged speech can alter normative expectations, shifting what counts as acceptable within a conversational space and, crucially, this occurs through identifiable mechanisms of social inference. Silence can make oppressive speech more effective precisely because it goes unopposed, allowing permissibility norms to change and authority to be conferred to the speaker.⁵ In addition, under standard models of social cognition, behaviour, including omission, serves as a cue for norm attribution, and concretely silence is often treated as acceptance, alignment or at least non-rejection, generating a default presumption of assent that places moral and epistemic pressure on bystanders to speak up.⁶ These considerations help explain that neutrality is *recognition-dependent*, and that a silent abstention in the face of hate speech risks complicity.

Importantly, the practical and moral costs of intervention cannot be ignored: counterspeech is frequently unsafe, ineffective, or counterproductive, particularly for members of marginalised groups⁷. Power asymmetries, social norms governing credibility and authority, and the unequal distribution of epistemic risk mean that speaking up can impose disproportionate burdens on direct or indirect targets, precisely those individuals already most vulnerable to harm.⁸ In such conditions, any general obligation to object appears to rely on idealised assumptions about equality, safety, and conversational control that are rarely satisfied.

These concerns are not merely theoretical. They are acutely felt in everyday public contexts—on public transport, in workplaces, and especially in online environments—where individuals encounter speech that is demeaning, derogatory, or exclusionary, yet feel unprepared to speak up or uncertain about how to respond. They may lack confidence in their epistemic standing, fear escalation or retaliation, or reasonably judge that their intervention will backfire or amplify the harm.⁹ As a result, abstention is often motivated not only by indifference or approval but by uncertainty, caution, or constrained agency. Nevertheless, as empirical studies have shown¹⁰, from the perspective of those targeted by the speech and third-party observers,

silence is often interpreted not as impartial restraint but as acceptance, acquiescence, or tacit alignment.

Understanding these dynamics requires attending not only to conversational norms but also to the structure of individuals' practical possibilities. Drawing on the notion of *affordances*, originally developed in ecological psychology, work in philosophy of language has emphasised that what agents can do with their words depends on their position within a network of social norms, expectations, and power relations.¹¹ The concept of *speech affordances* highlights that discursive actions are differentially enabled or constrained by social location. In non-ideal contexts, individuals may lack the affordances necessary for effective, safe, or intelligible intervention, even when they recognise the moral stakes.¹² Analyses of discursive injustice further demonstrate that these constraints are systematic rather than exceptional: some speakers are routinely misunderstood, dismissed, or sanctioned when they attempt to object.¹³

In this paper, we build on these insights while shifting the focus of analysis. Rather than asking whether agents are obligated to speak up, we examine the conditions under which remaining silent or non-intervention *could count* as neutrality. The central claim is that neutrality is *recognition-dependent*: non-intervention can function as neutrality only when it is *publicly recognisable as non-aligned*. In contexts structured by inequality and norm-sensitive interpretation, silence alone predictably fails to meet this condition. Even when abstention is motivated by legitimate concerns about safety, efficacy, or epistemic humility, it is often interpreted as taking sides¹⁴. The limits of abstention, therefore, arise not from individuals' intentions alone but from the group-level processes of social interpretation and norm inference through which actions and omissions are rendered meaningful. On this view, neutrality is not secured by refraining from intervention alone, but depends on whether abstention is taken up as non-alignment within a shared normative environment.

In adopting this framework, this account distinguishes between *passive neutrality*, understood as mere abstention or non-intervention, and *active neutrality*, which involves making one's non-alignment with hate and exclusionary speech *publicly recognisable*, without necessarily engaging in frontal confrontation. It defends the idea that neutrality must sometimes take an active but minimally expressive form to remain non-complicit. Crucially, although this distinction relies on behavioural markers, we reject an internalist conception of neutrality as defined solely by an agent's intentions or mental states. Instead, we adopt an externalist, recognition-dependent perspective that ensures non-alignment socially legible.

Methodologically, the analysis proceeds within a non-ideal framework, attending to the cognitive, normative, and social-epistemic constraints under which agents actually operate.¹⁵ Rather than asking what neutrality would require under full compliance, equal power, and perfect information, it examines how neutrality is perceived and operationalised in the social worlds individuals actually inhabit. The guiding question is not whether neutrality is conceptually coherent in the abstract, but under what conditions it can be obtained without reinforcing injustice.

The paper develops a non-ideal conceptual analysis of neutrality, drawing on empirical findings from moral psychology and cognitive science (to be addressed in detail in the following sections). These findings are not presented as independent normative premises, but as evidence about how behaviour is interpreted in practice. In particular, they clarify how silence and non-intervention—commonly used to enact non-interference—are understood in context. These interpretive mechanisms shape whether neutrality can be recognised as a social status, explaining why it cannot be self-declared, why silence is especially vulnerable to misinterpretation in unequal contexts, and why recognition is constitutive of neutrality.

The resulting account does not address the rightness of neutrality as an ethical aspiration under constrained agency; instead, it seeks to ensure that neutrality remains viable in non-ideal circumstances by identifying when silence and non-intervention fail as effective means of neutrality.

The Genealogy of Neutrality

The genealogical analysis that follows is not merely historical but methodological. Its purpose is to recover a structural feature of neutrality — its dependence on public recognition — that is often obscured in contemporary moral discourse. By examining how neutrality has been understood in legal and political contexts, the analysis identifies conditions that continue to apply when the concept is translated into everyday social settings. This feature is already visible in its earliest systematic formulations.

The concept of neutrality has its most systematically articulated origins in international law. Historically, neutrality referred to the legal and political status of states that abstained from participation in armed conflict between belligerents. To be neutral was not merely to refrain from military engagement, but to occupy a *recognised position defined by specific rights and duties*.¹⁶

Neutral states were expected to avoid providing material or strategic assistance, to ensure impartial treatment of belligerents, and to prevent their territory or resources from being used in ways that could advantage one side over another. Neutrality, even in its earliest formulations, was therefore not reducible to abstention or non-intervention; it was an institutionally structured and publicly legible stance, sustained through *observable practices and ongoing recognition by others*. A state's abstention counted as neutrality only insofar as it was acknowledged by relevant parties and *interpreted as non-aligned*.¹⁷ A formally neutral posture could collapse if abstention functioned, in practice, as support, facilitation, or tacit endorsement. This feature reveals a structural aspect of neutrality that is often obscured in everyday moral discourse: neutrality is not assessed solely in terms of internal intention or declared position, but *relationally*, in light of its public meaning and foreseeable effects.¹⁸

After the Second World War, the emergence of international human rights norms heightened this recognition-dependent nature, fundamentally altering the normative background against which abstention was evaluated. With the adoption of the United Nations Charter and the

Universal Declaration of Human Rights, peace, dignity, and the protection of fundamental rights came to be understood as collective responsibilities rather than optional commitments. Under these conditions, neutrality could no longer be treated as morally unqualified non-intervention. States were increasingly expected to ensure that their abstention did not enable, legitimate, or normalise genocide, crimes against humanity, or systematic violations of basic rights. Neutrality thus shifted from a purely negative stance—defined by non-participation—to a qualified and contingent posture, where its recognition as such became constrained by substantive moral obligations.¹⁹

This evolution is reflected in later developments in international law, including doctrines of humanitarian intervention and the *Responsibility to Protect*.²⁰ These frameworks reflect a growing consensus that neutrality must be compatible with preventing grave harm. The lesson is not that neutrality has been abandoned, but that its content has been refined. Abstention remains central, yet considerations of harm, responsibility, and recognition bound it. Neutrality comes to require not merely refraining from alignment, but also ensuring that one's non-intervention does not, in context, function as a mechanism of injustice.²¹

Despite these developments, in everyday moral reasoning, neutrality was further individualised, coming to denote a personal posture of non-intervention.²² Abstention is treated as self-sufficient, requiring no further justification beyond the individual's intention to “not take sides” with significant consequences.

By treating neutrality as an internal attitude or private moral choice, it often overlooks the fact that neutrality is attributed rather than merely adopted. Whether an individual behaviour counts as neutral depends on how their non-intervention is interpreted within a shared normative environment. The legal insight that neutrality must be *visible, credible, and publicly recognisable* is frequently lost. As a result, everyday moral accounts of neutrality underestimate the extent to which silence and non-intervention function as social signals that are interpreted against background norms of authority, responsibility, and alignment, rather than as purely private omissions.²³

Recovering the genealogical connection between legal and moral neutrality serves to counteract this tendency. Rather than collapsing moral neutrality into legal doctrine, this approach seeks to highlight their common structural foundations. In both domains, neutrality is constrained by background norms and assessed in light of its social meaning and predictable effects. When the normative background shifts—from sovereignty to human rights in international law, or from idealised equality to structural injustice in everyday social contexts—the conditions under which abstention can plausibly count as neutrality shift accordingly.

This genealogical background motivates a distinction between *formal neutrality*, defined by intention or structural position, and *recognised neutrality*, determined by social uptake and interpretation. Once this distinction is taken seriously, neutrality can no longer be treated as a default or morally inert stance. Instead, it emerges as a *socially mediated achievement* whose

stability depends on context, interpretation, and power distribution. In what follows, this insight is brought to bear on cases of bystander non-intervention in hate speech contexts, where abstention is common, often understandable, yet systematically vulnerable to misrecognition.

Passive Neutrality and Its Limits

Neutrality in morally charged contexts, such as hate speech, is commonly understood as passive non-intervention—remaining silent or refraining from action—a point already noted in the introduction. But if neutrality is a *socially recognised*, second-order status, can such first-order behaviours as silence and non-intervention ever succeed in realising it when interpreted by others in non-ideal contexts?

The conception of neutrality as passive non-intervention rests on a set of implicit assumptions. *First*, it assumes that abstention does not, in itself, constitute a meaningful contribution to the normative environment. *Second*, it presupposes that non-intervention will be interpreted as impartial by relevant observers. *Third*, it assumes that the background social context is sufficiently symmetric such that abstention does not predictably reinforce existing patterns of advantage or disadvantage. Once neutrality is exercised in non-ideal contexts marked by structural inequality and epistemic asymmetry, these assumptions break down.

From a social-epistemic perspective, neutrality cannot be evaluated independently of how others interpret actions and omissions. Individuals do not assess behaviour in isolation; they rely on contextual cues, shared expectations, and background norms to infer intentions and alignments.²⁴ Silence, in particular, is rarely perceived as empty. Empirical research shows that observers routinely treat non-intervention as informative, especially in morally salient situations. Silence is often taken as evidence of agreement, acceptance, or at least tolerance, particularly when the behaviour in question violates explicit or implicit norms.²⁵

These interpretative tendencies are not arbitrary. They rely on default inferential mechanisms that enable individuals to navigate complex social environments efficiently. From the perspective of philosophy of mind and cognitive science, social cognition operates through predictive models that are continuously updated based on observable behaviour.²⁶ When explicit dissent is absent, observers often infer that prevailing norms remain intact. In contexts where those norms are unjust or exclusionary, silence is therefore filled in by prior expectations, rendering abstention normatively one-sided despite an individual's intention to remain neutral.²⁷

Classic social-psychological studies of conformity and bystander behaviour show that individuals use others' actions and omissions as cues to determine what is socially acceptable.²⁸ In group settings, unresponsiveness can lead to pluralistic ignorance, in which individuals privately reject a norm while publicly complying because they infer that others accept it.²⁹ In such cases, silence does not preserve neutrality; it actively stabilises the norm

by preventing its contestation. The moral significance of abstention thus depends not only on what an individual does, but on how their behaviour interacts with collective inference.

Philosophically, these findings undermine the idea that neutrality is an intrinsic property of behaviour. Neutrality is relational: it depends on how abstention is situated within a network of social meanings and power relations.³⁰ This insight aligns with recognition-based accounts of normative status, according to which positions such as authority, credibility, or legitimacy exist only insofar as they are acknowledged by others.³¹ Neutrality, on this view, is not something one has; *it is something one is taken to have*.

The recognition condition has significant implications for *passive neutrality*. If those affected by hate or exclusionary speech cannot reasonably recognise a bystander's abstention as impartial, neutrality fails. This failure is not merely epistemic but constitutively normative. An individual cannot plausibly claim neutrality if their silence predictably contributes to harm or reinforces unjust structures, even if they neither intend nor endorse those outcomes.³² *Passive neutrality*, therefore, collapses under non-ideal conditions, not because neutrality is conceptually incoherent, but because abstention lacks the expressive resources required to secure recognition.

Importantly, this diagnosis does not entail that neutrality is impossible or that individuals are always morally required to intervene. Instead, it shows that neutrality cannot be equated with silence or non-intervention in contexts where silence is systematically misinterpreted. The instability of *passive neutrality* is a function of social context, not a conceptual flaw in the ideal itself. Once neutrality is understood as *recognition-dependent*, the limits of abstention become clear: remaining silent in hate speech contexts leaves your intentions unclear, yet others may draw strong conclusions about your stance.

The conclusion is therefore conditional. *Passive neutrality* may be viable under idealised conditions in which background norms are just, power relations are symmetric, and abstention is reliably interpreted as impartial. In non-ideal contexts, however, these conditions do not obtain. There, passive neutrality is unstable and predictably one-sided. Recognising this instability is a necessary step towards developing an alternative account of neutrality that remains faithful to its ethical motivations while acknowledging the realities of social interpretation. The following sections build on this reconstruction by examining paradigmatic cases in which *passive neutrality* fails and by articulating the conditions under which neutrality can be *actively* secured.

Neutrality as a Recognition-Dependent Social Practice

The preceding analysis motivates a reconceptualisation of neutrality in hate speech contexts, not as a simple behavioural category, but as a second-order social practice. To be neutral is not merely to refrain from action or judgement; it is to occupy a publicly recognisable position of non-alignment that does not contribute to harm. Neutrality, in such a context, is not an intrinsic property of silence or non-intervention, but a relational status constituted

through social interpretation and uptake. Whether neutrality obtains depends on how an agent's behaviour is perceived, classified, and integrated into the shared normative environment.

This *recognition-dependent* account finds support in both legal theory and social epistemology. In international law, neutrality is valid only to the extent recognised by the relevant parties; internal declarations carry little normative weight unless accompanied by publicly legible practices that render non-alignment credible.³³ A structurally analogous logic applies in everyday moral contexts: An individual's intention to remain neutral cannot secure neutrality unless others can recognise their stance as impartial and non-harmful.

Social epistemology helps explain why recognition plays this constitutive role. Epistemic statuses such as credibility, authority, and trust are not private attributes but socially distributed positions sustained through shared interpretative practices.³⁴ Neutrality functions similarly. It exists only insofar as it is taken up as a legitimate stance within a community. Where such uptake fails, neutrality does not merely go unacknowledged; it fails to exist as a social fact.

From the perspective of philosophy of mind, this generates a representational gap between mental states and social meaning. An agent may sincerely intend to remain neutral, yet intention alone underdetermines how behaviour will be interpreted. This highlights the internalist/externalist tension with respect to neutrality mentioned above: the internalist view locates neutrality in agents' intentions, while the externalist view emphasises the social interpretation of their actions. Silence provides minimal information about motivational structure while simultaneously inviting observers to rely on background expectations and default heuristics.³⁵ In contexts structured by inequality, these defaults are systematically biased in favour of dominant norms, often defeating the individual's intention.

This gap exposes a limitation of internalist accounts of moral agency. Mental neutrality—the lack of commitment to or endorsement of hate and exclusionary practices—cannot by itself ground social neutrality. The transition from intention to *publicly recognisable* stance requires communicative behaviour capable of constraining interpretation.³⁶ Silence, by its nature, lacks this capacity. It creates a representational vacuum that is filled by socially available priors. Importantly, neutrality is unevenly accessible across social positions. Individuals occupy epistemic locations that shape how their actions and omissions are interpreted: Members of dominant groups may be more readily presumed neutral, while marginalised agents are denied this presumption.³⁷ Their silence may be read as acquiescence, fear, or internalised subordination rather than impartial restraint. This asymmetry reflects structural differences in access to credibility and recognition, not differences in intention.

These considerations support two conclusions. First, neutrality must be understood as an achieved position dependent on signalling, uptake, and social interpretation. Second, mere silence or non-intervention is a poor vehicle for securing this position in non-ideal contexts, particularly in group settings where collective inaction amplifies interpretative pressures and

collapses the possibility of recognising neutrality.³⁸ Acknowledging these limits does not turn neutrality into an impossible aspiration; it clarifies the conditions under which neutrality can be realised without predictably reinforcing harm. The following section develops an alternative model—active neutrality—that responds to these conditions while preserving the core motivations underlying neutrality.

Active Neutrality: Conditions, Constraints, and Normative Structure

If neutrality is recognition-dependent, the inadequacy of passive neutrality in non-ideal contexts motivates an alternative model—*active neutrality*—that enables non-intervention without predictably reinforcing injustice. In hate speech contexts, *active neutrality* is not moral interventionism or advocacy (It does not require individuals to promote substantive moral views or align with particular groups or movements); instead, it involves limited action aimed at disrupting the inferential mechanisms that lead to silence being interpreted as endorsement. Its core function is communicative: to make non-alignment with hate and exclusionary speech *publicly legible* where abstention alone fails to do so. Importantly, this communicative dimension need not be exhausted by verbal objection (counterspeech)³⁹. Where speech is ineffective, ignored, or disproportionately costly, active neutrality may be realised through alternative signalling practices that clarify stance without escalating moral confrontation.⁴⁰

Crucially, this account does not impose a general obligation on agents to signal their stance. Rather, it specifies the conditions under which neutrality can be realised as a socially recognisable status. In contexts where these conditions cannot be met—due to risk, power asymmetries, or lack of uptake—neutrality may be structurally unavailable. This limitation reflects constraints on social interpretation rather than a failure on the part of individual agents.

The normative structure of active neutrality can be articulated in terms of three conditions. *First, the recognisability condition*: behaviour must provide observers with sufficient cues to distinguish non-intervention from alignment with harmful discourses. While this may sometimes involve minimal verbal objection, it can also be satisfied through contextual or nonverbal signalling that makes ethical restraint perceptually salient. *Second, the proportionality condition*: the form and intensity of signalling must correspond to the social stakes, ensuring that the effort to secure recognisability does not collapse into moralising overreach. Third, the *non-alignment condition*: *active neutrality* should avoid endorsing alternative substantive positions, thereby preventing harmful norms from stabilising while preserving restraint. Together, these conditions delimit a space in which neutrality remains meaningful without being socially misleading.

Rather than attempting to specify an exhaustive set of practices, this account points towards a space of context-sensitive ways in which non-alignment may become perceptually available to others. The account gains further precision when situated within a broader account of communicative meaning, acknowledging that it arises not only through semantic processing

but also through perceptual and social simulation.⁴¹ For example, maintaining visual engagement with an incident, orienting one's body towards those targeted, or remaining visibly attentive are rapidly processed as indicators of interactional structure and may be registered as a form of disalignment with the speaker, even in the absence of overt intervention.⁴² Similarly, research on social perception and symbolic action supports the idea that visual and performative signals such as facial and bodily gestures, colours, coordinated symbols, or other visible markers can condense complex moral stances into salient, widely intelligible forms, often achieving greater diffusion and affective resonance than verbal rebuttal.⁴³

Such responses translate the *recognisability condition* into perceptually salient cues, allowing observers to infer abstention without engaging in direct confrontation or aligning with any particular group. For example, nonverbal responses that transmit an embrace of democratic values—such as tolerance and inclusivity—through symbols, colours, coordinated gestures, or shared insignia may operationalise *active neutrality* in settings where conventional verbal signalling is improbable or impractical.

Empirical and theoretical research on social movements and symbolic resistance further clarifies the effectiveness of these interventions: Visual and performative cues can condense complex moral stances into accessible, interpretable signals that communicate disalignment with harmful speech and shape collective behaviour.⁴⁴ These cues often achieve greater diffusion, emotional resonance, and trust than textual or verbal counterspeech alone, making them particularly suitable in public contexts where normative boundaries must be conveyed swiftly and visibly.

Furthermore, studies of real-world hate speech incidents further suggest that observers distinguish sharply between mere co-presence and perceptible disalignment, indicating that the social meaning of non-intervention depends in part on whether attention and stance are made visible.⁴⁵ What matters, then, is not the adoption of any particular signalling form, but whether available cues are sufficient to reduce interpretive ambiguity and render non-alignment intelligible within a given context.

Active neutrality thus benefits from a broader repertoire of communicative strategies that provide interpretable cues, reducing the underdetermination inherent in silence and constraining plausible inferences. Symbols such as badges or performative motifs may function simultaneously as markers of disalignment and as pre-emptive establishment of harmful social norms, by instituting expectations of inclusion and tolerance that operate prior to, or in parallel with, episodes of hate speech.⁴⁶

Integrating these strategies into the framework of active neutrality demonstrates how non-intervention in hate speech contexts can be practically realised, attending to both structural constraints and the communicative mechanisms through which non-alignment is socially recognised. Yet the practical reach of these communicative resources is not unlimited—this account acknowledges legitimate constraints on agency: when recognisability cannot be

secured, neutrality may be unreachable, reflecting, however, structural rather than individual limitations.

Theoretical and Practical Implications for Institutions, Policy and Civic Life

The *recognition-dependent* account of neutrality developed here highlights that silence or non-intervention in hate-speech contexts cannot be assumed as a default or a morally inert option.⁴⁷ *Active neutrality* must be actively achieved: it depends on social interpretation and recognition by others. This reframing complements debates on omission, moral permissibility, and complicity, clarifying how silence functions within shared normative frameworks, explaining why neutrality often fails in practice, and how it can be actively secured. Similarly, it connects discussions of moral responsibility in hate-speech contexts with empirical evidence showing that abstention can constitute complicity without intent or explicit endorsement. It allows distinguishing between cases in which individuals can sustain a neutral stance of non-intervention and those in which structural constraints make this aspiration impossible. Responsibility thus emerges as an interplay between intention and social interpretation rather than internal states alone.

Furthermore, the *recognition-dependent* account has direct implications for institutional design, public policy, and everyday civic practices. Institutions often appeal to neutrality in responding to controversial speech, adopting policies of non-interference or procedural distance. While intended to protect pluralism and academic freedom, silence in the face of exclusionary or demeaning speech can inadvertently signal tolerance of harmful norms. Recognition-sensitive neutrality requires institutions to distinguish clearly between refraining from adjudicating contested viewpoints and allowing speech acts that marginalise or silence members of the community. Institutional signalling that reaffirms commitments to dignity and inclusion can preserve neutrality while preventing silence from being interpreted as acquiescence.

The same logic applies to workplaces, public services, and civic organisations. In these settings, neutrality is often equated with professional restraint or emotional detachment. Yet when harmful speech occurs in shared spaces, collective silence amplifies perceived harm and normalises exclusionary behaviour. Empirical evidence indicates that individual neutrality may be intelligible in isolation, but collective neutrality is rarely recognised as such. Organisations should therefore adopt accessible, non-confrontational protocols for signalling non-alignment, enabling members to maintain neutrality without escalating conflict or imposing moral conformity.

At the public policy level, this account informs hate speech regulation and counterspeech initiatives. Policies that rely solely on sanctions or legal prohibitions may overlook the social mechanisms that perpetuate harm. Complementary, practices that foster visible, collective expressions of non-alignment with exclusionary norms—such as affirmations of shared democratic and inclusive norms, public statements or civic campaigns—can operationalise *active neutrality*, reducing ambiguity of silence and making clear that non-intervention in

complex social environments does not entail tolerance of harm. These practices do not demand moral heroism; they recalibrate default interpretive frameworks so that abstention does not systematically reinforce dominant or exclusionary norms.

Ultimately, neutrality functions as a civic virtue only when embedded in socially legible practices, it requires that abstention is recognisable as non-alignment by those affected. *Passive neutrality* presumes idealised symmetry that rarely obtains in pluralistic societies. *Active neutrality*, by contrast, attends to the social and epistemic dimensions of abstention, mitigating its harmful effects through minimal, recognition-oriented signalling. Institutions and policies that incorporate this insight can better align commitments to neutrality with the realities of social interaction under conditions of inequality.

Conclusions

This article has argued that neutrality in the context of hate speech cannot be reduced to silence or abstention. Far from being a morally inert baseline, neutrality is a recognition-dependent, socially mediated achievement that must be actively sustained. *Passive neutrality*—simply refraining from action—fails in contexts where background norms are structured by inequality and prejudice. In such situations, silence is never socially empty: it acquires meaning, often reinforcing exclusionary or harmful norms, even when individuals intend to remain impartial.⁴⁷

Neutrality is not a property of isolated actions, nor is it secured by internal intention alone. In incidents of hate speech, it is a second-order social practice whose effectiveness depends on how others interpret and respond to one's abstention. Drawing on the philosophy of language, social epistemology, and empirical social cognition and moral psychology, this article shows that silence functions as an evidential input in collective processes of norm inference. In group settings, particularly those involving hate or discriminatory speech, abstention is rarely neutral in effect, even when motivated by impartiality.

These insights motivate a shift from *passive* to *active neutrality* in hate speech contexts. *Active neutrality* does not abandon the ethical aspiration of non-interference, nor does it mandate overt confrontation in all cases. Instead, it consists of minimal, *recognition-sensitive* signalling that prevents abstention from being misread as endorsement or complicity. By emphasising visibility, context, and interpretability, active neutrality preserves the core ethical intuition of neutrality while adapting it to the social realities of non-ideal environments.

The contribution of this analysis is both conceptual and methodological. Conceptually, it offers a refined account of neutrality that integrates moral philosophy, social epistemology, philosophy of mind, cognitive science, and legal theory. Methodologically, it demonstrates the value of combining empirical insight with philosophical reflection: in morally charged contexts as hate speech, neutrality is not an abstract ideal to be assumed but a fragile achievement, realised only through socially intelligible action.

Ultimately, neutrality in these contexts is meaningful only when it is actively recognised. Any adequate theory of neutrality must account for the interpretive mechanisms through which abstention is read, and the structural conditions under which recognition is possible. In societies marked by persistent inequality and social hierarchies, acknowledging these dynamics is essential if neutrality is to remain a defensible and morally significant ideal in the face of hate and exclusion.

Footnotes:

¹ John M. Darley; Bibb Latané: *Bystander intervention in emergencies: diffusion of responsibility*, in: *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 8 (1968) 377–383; Bibb Latané and John Darley, *The Unresponsive Bystander: Why Doesn't He Help?* (New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts, 1970); Amalia Álvarez-Benjumea and Fabian Winter, “Normative Change and Culture of Hate: An Experiment in Online Environments,” *European Sociological Review* 34, no. 3 (2018): 223–237.

² Rae Langton: Blocking as Counter-Speech, in: *New Work on Speech Acts*, ed. by Daniel Fogal; Daniel W. Harris et al. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018) 144–156; Sandy Goldberg, *Conversational Pressure* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2020); Jennifer Saul: Someone Is Wrong on the Internet: Is There an Obligation to Correct False and Oppressive Speech on Social Media?, in *The Epistemology of Deceit in a Postdigital Era*, ed. A. MacKenzie et al. (Springer, 2021); Saray Ayala-López, “Speech Affordances: A Structural Take on How Much We Can Do with Our Words,” *European Journal of Philosophy* 24 (2016): 879–891.

³ R. Langton: Blocking as Counter-Speech, op. cit.; S. Goldberg, *Conversational Pressure*, op. cit.; J. Saul: Someone Is Wrong on the Internet, op. cit..

⁴ R.Langton: Blocking as Counter-Speech, op. cit.; Saray Ayala and Nadya Vasilyeva, "Responsibility for Silence", *Journal of Social Philosophy* 47, n.º 2 (2016): 205.

⁵ Mary Kate McGowan, *Speech and Harm* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2019); Mary Kate McGowan, “Responding to Harmful Speech,” in Johnson (ed.), *Voicing Dissent* (2018); Rae Langton: The Authority of Hate Speech, in: *Oxford Studies in Philosophy of Law* 3, ed. by John Gardner; Leslie Green et al. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018) 123–152.

⁶ Saul: Someone Is Wrong on the Internet, op. cit.; Goldberg: *Conversational Pressure*, op. cit.; R. Langton: *Blocking as Counter-Speech*, op. cit.

⁷ Czopp, Alexander M.; Margo J. Monteith: Confronting prejudice (literally): reactions to confrontations of racial and gender bias, in: *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin* 29/4 (2003) 532–544; Dickter, Cheryl L.; Victoria A. Newton: To confront or not to confront: non-targets' evaluations of and responses to racist comments, in: *Journal of Applied Social Psychology* 43 (2013) E262–E275.

⁸Jason W. Howard: Terror, hate and the demands of counter-speech, in: *British Journal of Political Science* 51/3 (2021) 924–939; R. Langton: *Blocking as Counter-Speech*, op. cit., 149; Ishani Maitra, “Subordinating Speech,” in Maitra and McGowan (eds.), *Speech and Harm* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012); Saul (2021); Nielsen, Laura Beth: Power in public, in: *Speech and Harm*, ed. by Ishani Maitra; Mary Kate McGowan (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012) 148–173.

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